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Assessment of surface water quality status of the Aghien Lagoon and its tributaries Under Multiple Anthropogenic Pressures

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Abstract

This study assesses the chemical and physico-chemical quality of the waters of the Aghien lagoon and its main tributaries, located in southern Ivory Coast, against a backdrop of significant human pressure linked to rapid urbanisation, agricultural activities and inadequate sanitation. The Aghien Lagoon is a strategic resource with the potential to contribute to the drinking water supply for the Abidjan district. Sampling was carried out during the wet season (June 2023) and dry season (August 2023) at several stations distributed between the lagoon and its tributaries (Bété, Djibi and Mé). The physico-chemical parameters measured included temperature, pH, electrical conductivity, dissolved oxygen, turbidity, and nitrogen and phosphorus nutrients. In the tributaries, several parameters show significant differences ($p < 0.05$), notably electrical conductivity, turbidity, ammonium, nitrites, total nitrogen, total phosphorus and BOD. In the Aghien lagoon, only a few variables, such as nitrites, total nitrogen and total phosphorus, show significant variations. Concentrations of BOD₅, COD and the organic pollution index (OPI) were also determined to assess the level of organic pollution in the water. The results indicate warm water with low mineral content and, overall, a slightly alkaline pH. However, high levels of turbidity, total nitrogen, nitrates and total phosphorus reflect a significant influence from anthropogenic inputs and runoff. COD and BOD₅ concentrations reveal a relatively high organic load, but one that is predominantly biodegradable, with COD/BOD ratios below 3. The organic pollution index indicates moderate to high organic pollution at several monitoring points, particularly in tributaries and at confluence points.

Keywords : Evolution, water quality, organic pollution, Djibi River

Introduction

The rapid growth of cities, particularly in peri-urban areas, has been one of the major environmental challenges of recent decades (Salem and Tsurusaki, 2024). Unplanned or inadequately controlled urbanisation is leading to the increasing artificialisation of land, an increase in domestic and industrial waste, and greater pressure on natural resources, particularly watercourses (Seifollahi-Aghmiuni *et al.*, 2022). In this context, peri-urban surface water, located on the boundary between urban and rural areas, are suffering severe disruption to their physico-chemical and biological quality.

These aquatic environments, which used to be relatively unspoilt, are now becoming receptors for a wide range of pollutants: untreated wastewater, pollutant-laden urban run-off, agricultural effluents and uncontrolled waste dumping (Miyittah *et al.*, 2020). The impact of

these pressures is often exacerbated by the absence or inadequacy of sewerage infrastructure, which is characteristic of rapidly expanding areas (Bashir *et al.*, 2020; Siziba and Sero, 2022; Varatharajan *et al.*, 2025). The result is a gradual deterioration in water quality, compromising not only domestic, agricultural and recreational uses, but also aquatic biodiversity and ecological balances.

In Ivory Coast, Aghien Lagoon, located in the southern part of the country, represents one of the major freshwater resources with the potential to contribute to the drinking water supply of the Abidjan District in response to rapid population growth and increasing pressure on groundwater resources (Koffi *et al.*, 2018; Koffi *et al.*, 2019; Yéo *et al.*, 2023). This tropical lagoon, mainly fed by the Bété, Djibi and Mé rivers, also plays an important ecological and socio-economic role for the surrounding communities.

However, the watershed of Aghien Lagoon has been subjected for several years to significant anthropogenic pressure associated with rapid urbanisation, agricultural activities, domestic waste discharges and inadequate sanitation practices (Diallo *et al.*, 2019). These activities promote the input of organic matter, nutrients and various contaminants into the lagoon through its tributaries, resulting in the gradual deterioration of water quality. Previous studies have highlighted high concentrations of organic matter and ammonium, as well as a decline in the bacteriological quality of the lagoon waters (Humbert, 2012; Mitroi *et al.*, 2024).

Furthermore, the hydrological dynamics of the tributaries strongly influence the physico-chemical and chemical characteristics of the lagoon system, particularly through runoff processes, nutrient transport, and the transfer of pollutants from the watershed. Knowledge of the chemical quality of the lagoon waters and its main tributaries therefore appears essential for the sustainable management of this strategic resource (Koffi *et al.*, 2019; Yeo *et al.*, 2023). It is within this context that the present study was conducted, with the aim of assessing the chemical quality of the waters of the Aghien Lagoon and its main tributaries through the analysis of several indicators of water pollution and mineralisation. This study therefore seeks to provide a better understanding of the current state of the aquatic environment and the influence of anthropogenic activities on water quality within the watershed of the Aghien Lagoon.

Material and Methods

Study area

Fig. 1 illustrates a map of the study area. Aghien Lagoon is located at the North of the Ebrié Lagoon between the latitudes 5°22'N and 5°26'N and the Longitudes 3°49'W and 3°55'W. The total area of the lagoon is about 20 km² and its depth varies from 1 to 14 m. The climate is typically equatorial, characterized by four seasons including a large dry season from December to March, a major rainy season from April to July, a small dry season from August to September and a small rainy season From October to November. The catchment of the Aghien Lagoon is located in a covered area by dense evergreen and rain forest (Diallo *et al.*, 2019). The main crops grown by these farmers are those of market gardeners, Oil palms, coffee, cocoa, hevea, and banana trees (plantain). Activities related to the lagoon environment are mainly fisheries, fish farming, transportation and exploitation of sand quarries.

Table 1. Description of sampling location

Site Name	Station codes	Geographical coordinates	Site description
Bété	R1	Longitude : 03°57'13.8"W Latitude : 05°29'32.7"N	Located upstream of the Bete River
Mé	R2	Longitude : 03°50'00.0" W Latitude : 05°28'26.9" N	Located upstream of the Me River
Djibi	R3	Longitude : 03°56'09.8"W Latitude : 05°26'20.1" N	Sample taken at the mouth of the Djibi River
Confluence Me/chenal	C1	Longitude : 03°49'40.0" W Latitude : 05°22'51.9" N	Located at the confluence of the Me River and the channel
Channel	C2	Longitude : 03°49'53.5" W Latitude : 05°22'47.2" N	Located on the outflow channel of the Aghien lagoon
Aghien	A1	Longitude : 03°51'03.0" W Latitude : 05°24'21.0" N	A spot on the lagoon near Aghien and Akoyaté villages
Akandjé	A2	Longitude : 03°53'52.7" W Latitude : 05°25'23.9" N	A spot on the Aghien lagoon near the Akandjé village
Eleaeis	A3	Longitude : 03°52'11.8" W Latitude : 05°25'10.8" N	View of the Aghien lagoon near the Eleaeis palm plantation
Confluence Bété/Aghien	A4	Longitude : 03°54'37.2" W Latitude : 05°25'45.3" N	Point located at the confluence of the Aghien Lagoon and the Bete
Confluence Djibi/Aghien	A5	Longitude : 03°55'15.07' W Latitude : 05°25'36.8544 N	Point located at the confluence of the Aghien Lagoon and the Djibi River

Data processing tools and statistical analysis

The QGIS Desktop software, version 10.7 was used to generate the Fig. 1 using the coordinates of the twenty-two sites. Statistical analyses such as principal component analysis (PCA) were carried out by using R softwares (Version 3.6.0). Principal component analysis (PCA) was carried out to determine the likely sources of contamination and the geochemical factors controlling the distribution of pollutants in the waters of the Aghien lagoon and tributary (Liu *et al.*, 2018). On the other hand, Kruskal–Wallis test in ANOVA analysis was also used to determine the significant differences between seasonal campaigns. Differences between means were considered significant when p value < 0.05 .

Determination of the organic pollution index (OPI)

To assess the organic load in the river, the Organic Pollution Index (OPI) of Leclercq (2001) was also used. The principle of the IPO is to divide the values of polluting elements into 05 classes (Table 2). This index is obtained by means of ammonium, BOD, nitrite and phosphate values. The basic idea behind the calculation is to divide the values of the three polluting factors into five classes, and then identify the corresponding class number for each parameter using the average data in Table 1 and the values obtained in this study. The final organic pollution index is the average of the pollution classes for all the parameters (Bekri *et al.*, 2020).

Table 2 : Grid of organic pollution index classes (Leclercq, 2001)

Classes	NH ₄ ⁺ (mg/l)	BOD (mgO ₂ /l)	PO ₄ ³⁻ (µg/l)	NO ₂ ⁻ (µg/l)	Limits of classes	Characterisation of pollution
5	>15	< 2	< 15	< 0.1	4.6 - 5.0	None
4	0.1-0.9	2.1 - 5	16 - 75	0.1 - 0.9	4.0 - 4.5	Low
3	1-2.4	5.1-10	76 - 250	1 - 2.4	3.0 - 3.9	Moderate
2	2.5-6	10.1 - 15	251 - 900	2.5 - 6	2.0 - 2.9	High
1	>6	>15	> 900	> 6	1.0 - 1.9	Very strong

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The physicochemical characteristics of the Aghien Lagoon

The descriptive statistical data of water quality in the lagoon are summarized in Table 3. Results indicate warm waters with near-neutral to slightly alkaline pH conditions. Low mean values of electrical conductivity (EC), TDS, and salinity reflect weak mineralization of the water body. Dissolved oxygen (DO) concentrations were generally moderate, although low minimum values may indicate localized oxygen depletion (Liang *et al.*, 2023; Zhanga *et al.*, 2025). Turbidity exhibited strong spatial variability, with very high maximum values suggesting substantial inputs of suspended particles into the aquatic environment (Wu *et al.*, 2025). Furthermore, the identical values observed for June and August may reflect stable environmental conditions or potential data redundancy.

Table 3. Statistical summary of water physicochemical quality in the Aghien lagoon and tributary during the wet (June 2023) and dry (auguste 2023) seasons

Parameter	T (°C)	pH	EC (µS/cm)	TDS (ppm)	DO (mg/L)	DO (%)	Salinity (PSU)	Turbidity (NTU)
June								
Min	26.5	6.1	60.4	26	1.32	25.7	0.01	48.3
Max	32.09	8.5	224.6	126	7.7	97.5	0.06	1274
Mean	29.34	7.36	86.74	43.95	4.77	68.33	0.03	191.44
Standard deviation	1.98	0.71	49.32	29.35	2.03	23.55	0.01	381.05
August								
Min	26.5	6.1	60.4	26	1.32	25.7	0.01	48.3
Max	32.09	8.5	224.6	126	7.7	97.5	0.06	1274
Moyenne	29.34	7.36	86.74	43.95	4.77	68.33	0.03	191.44
Standard deviation	1.98	0.71	49.32	29.35	2.03	23.55	0.01	381.05

Nutrient parameters showed significant spatial and seasonal variability during the June and August sampling campaigns. In June, total nitrogen (TN) concentrations ranged from 1.7 to 9.77 mg/L, with an average of 3.2 ± 2.43 mg/L, whilst total phosphorus (TP) ranged from 0.18 to 1.28 mg/L, with an average of 0.46 ± 0.31 mg/L. Nitrate concentrations were relatively high, ranging from 5.2 to 14.6 mg/L, with an average of 7.65 ± 2.78 mg/L. These high nitrate levels likely reflect inputs from agricultural activities, domestic wastewater or soil leaching during rainy periods. Several recent studies show that anthropogenic nitrogen inputs

are now one of the main factors contributing to the degradation of aquatic ecosystems and the eutrophication of water bodies (Ladha *et al.*, 2005; Singh and Craswell, 2021).

Nitrite concentrations remained relatively low in June (0.03–0.086 mg/L; mean: 0.049 ± 0.01 mg/L), suggesting relatively active nitrification in the aquatic environment. In contrast, ammonium concentrations showed considerable variability (0.45 – 6.47 mg/L; mean: 1.17 ± 1.86 mg/L), likely indicating localised inputs of organic matter or low-oxygen conditions favoring the accumulation of reduced forms of nitrogen (Xia *et al.*, 2013). Phosphate concentrations ranged from 0.017 to 0.16 mg/L, with a mean of 0.07 ± 0.05 mg/L. Even at low concentrations, phosphorus can strongly stimulate biological productivity in inland waters, where it is often the limiting factor in eutrophication processes.

In August, TN concentrations ranged from 1.13 to 8.85 mg/L, with an average of 3.04 ± 2.18 mg/L, values that were broadly similar to those observed in June. However, TP showed a notable increase, reaching a maximum of 1.98 mg/L and an average of 0.86 ± 0.61 mg/L. This increase could be linked to increased runoff, the resuspension of sediments or diffuse inputs from human activities in the catchment area. Recent research highlights that the release of phosphorus from sediments and human activities plays a major role in maintaining eutrophication in aquatic environments (Van Cappellen, 2023; Morelle *et al.* 2024).

Table 4. Statistical summary of nutrient in Aghien lagoon during the wet (June) and dry (Auguste) seasons

Parameter	TN (mg/L)	TP (mg/L)	Nitrate (mg/L)	Nitrite (mg/L)	Ammonium (mg/L)	Phosphates (mg/L)
June						
Min	1.7	0.18	5.2	0.03	0.45	0.017
Max	9.77	1.28	14.6	0.086	6.47	0.16
Mean	3.2	0.46	7.65	0.049	1.17	0.07
Standard deviation	2.43	0.31	2.78	0.01	1.86	0.05
August						
Min	1.13	0.156	3.9	0.007	0.35	0.016
Max	8.85	1.98	10.7	0.066	6.1	0.19
Mean	3.04	0.86	6.66	0.02	1.155	0.08
Standard deviation	2.18	0.61	2.37	0.01	1.74	0.06

Changes in COD and BOD

The results obtained show COD concentrations ranging from 18.4 to 31.9 mgO₂/L in June, with an average of 24.16 ± 4.45 mgO₂/L, whilst in August, they ranged from 19.5 to 27.1 mgO₂/L, with an average of 23.01 ± 2.88 mgO₂/L (Table 5). BOD₅ values also showed moderate variability, with averages of 13.88 ± 2.81 mgO₂/L in June and 11.9 ± 2.33 mgO₂/L in August. These levels reflect the presence of a relatively high organic load in the waters studied, likely linked to domestic inputs, natural organic matter and surface runoff.

The COD/BOD ratio varies between 1.69 and 2.55, with averages of 1.74 in June and 1.93 in August. Ratios below 3 generally indicate that the organic matter is predominantly biodegradable (Choi *et al.*, 2017), suggesting that the pollution observed is primarily of organic origin and potentially biodegradable. The slight increase in the ratio in August could indicate a slightly higher proportion of less readily biodegradable organic matter during this

period. Overall, the low standard deviations observed indicate a relative spatial homogeneity of the measured parameters.

Table 5. Statistical summary of COD and BOD in Aghien lagoon and tributary during the wet (June) and dry (Auguste) seasons

Parameter	June			August		
	COD (mgO ₂ /L)	BOD (mgO ₂ /L)	COD/BOD ratio	COD (mgO ₂ /L)	BOD (mgO ₂ /L)	COD/BOD ratio
Min	18.4	7.2	2.55	19.5	8	2.43
Max	31.9	18	1.77	27.1	16	1.69
Moy	24.16	13.88	1.74	23.01	11.9	1.93
Standard deviation	4.45	2.81	0.43	2.88	2.33	0.32

The table 6 presents the p-values associated with variations in physico-chemical and nutrient parameters in the tributaries, the Aghien lagoon and between the two environments. In the tributaries, several parameters show significant differences (p<0.05), notably electrical conductivity, turbidity, ammonium, nitrites, total nitrogen, total phosphorus and BOD, reflecting a strong influence of anthropogenic inputs and runoff.

Table 6. Summary of the results of the Kruskal-Wallis tests showing the spatial variation in physicochemical parameters. In bold: statistically significant correlation coefficients at the p = 0.05 level

Explanatory variable	Tributary rivers	Aghien Lagoon	Tributary vs Aghien Lagoon
Temperature	0.111	0.622	0.08
pH	0.757	0.968	0.04
Electrical Conductivity	< 0.003	0.171	< 0.001
Salinity	0.03	0.833	0.012
% OD	0.01	0.061	0.026
Turbidity	< 0.001	0.935	0.002
Ammonium	< 0.001	0.399	< 0.001
Nitrate	0.041	0.119	0.036
Nitrite	0.022	0.017	< 0.001
TN	< 0.001	0.038	0.021
TP	0.002	0.002	< 0.001
Phosphates	0.136	0.073	0.007
BOD	< 0.001	0.092	0.038
COD	0.077	0.097	0.179

In the Aghien lagoon, only a few variables, such as nitrites, total nitrogen and total phosphorus, show significant variations, indicating greater homogeneity of the lagoon waters. A comparison between the tributaries and the lagoon also reveals significant differences for several parameters, particularly conductivity, turbidity, nutrients and BOD, highlighting the influence of the tributaries on the quality of the lagoon waters.

Organic Pollution Index (OPI)

Fig.2 shows the trend in the organic pollution index (OPI) measured at the various sampling sites (R1 to A5) during June and August. The recorded values generally range from 2 to 3.7, indicating a level of organic pollution ranging from moderate to high according to the classification thresholds shown in the figure. This spatial and temporal variability may be linked to differences in the intensity of human activities around the sites, to the input of organic matter from runoff, and to seasonal hydrological conditions. The relatively high IPO values observed at several stations reflect a significant organic load, likely influenced by domestic discharges, agricultural activities or natural inputs of organic matter (Bounab, 2025). However, the absence of values below 2 suggests that the waters studied do not exhibit a very severe state of organic pollution.

In June, the majority of sites recorded values close to or above 3, notably sites C2, A3 and A5, which corresponds to moderate to low organic pollution according to the scale used. Site R3 recorded the lowest value (≈ 2.3), indicating more pronounced organic pollution. In August, an increase in the IPO was observed at certain sites, particularly R1, C2, A2 and A5, where the indices reached or exceeded 3.3. Conversely, sites A3 and A4 showed a relative decrease in values.

Fig. 2. Classification of pollution levels according to the organic pollution index value category

Principal Components Approach

The PCA for the analyses carried out in June (the rainy season) shows that the first two principal components account for 75.8% of the total variance, indicating that the physico-chemical parameters are well represented (Fig. 3). Axis 1 is mainly associated with salinity, suspended solids, turbidity and ammonium, reflecting the influence of anthropogenic inputs and water mineralisation. Conversely, BOD and COD are negatively correlated with this axis. The distribution of sites highlights spatial heterogeneity in water quality, with site R3 standing out, characterised by high particulate and nitrogen loads. These results suggest the influence of human activities and runoff inputs on the physico-chemical dynamics of the

water, as reported in several studies on tropical lagoon environments (APHA, 2017; Alkhadher *et al.* 2025).

For the analyses carried out in August (Fig. 4), the first two principal component axes account for 65.3% of the total variance, with 46.3 % attributable to axis 1 and 19 % to axis 2, indicating that the data are well represented.

Axis 1 is mainly associated with parameters relating to mineralisation and nutrient pollution (TDS, conductivity, ammonium, phosphates, salinity and nitrites), whilst COD and dissolved oxygen are negatively correlated with it. Axis 2 contrasts nitrates with organic pollution parameters such as BOD and turbidity.

Fig. 3. a Histogram of variance percent; b Principal component analyses (PCA) of the average of physical–chemical parameters. C Biplot for Sampling sites on Aghien lagoon and tributary in June (wet season)

Fig. 4. a Histogram of variance percent; b Principal component analyses (PCA) of the average of physical–chemical parameters. C Biplot for Sampling sites on Aghien lagoon and tributary in August (Dry season)

The distribution of stations reveals marked spatial variability in water quality in August. Site R3 stands out for its high loads of dissolved salts and nutrients, reflecting a greater anthropogenic influence. Sites A2, A3, A4 and A5 exhibit relatively similar characteristics, whilst R2 and C1 are more strongly associated with organic pollution.

Conclusion

The present study highlighted the influence of anthropogenic activities and seasonal dynamics on the water quality of the Aghien Lagoon and its tributaries. The results revealed moderate mineralisation, significant turbidity, and relatively high concentrations of nutrients and

organic matter, indicating inputs from agricultural runoff, domestic wastewater, and diffuse pollution sources. COD/BOD₅ ratios below 3 suggest that the organic pollution is mainly biodegradable. The Organic Pollution Index indicated moderate to high organic pollution levels across most sampling sites, while statistical analyses showed significant spatial and seasonal variations in several physicochemical parameters. PCA results further confirmed the influence of nutrient enrichment, suspended matter, and mineralisation processes on water quality variability. Overall, the study demonstrates that increasing human pressures are progressively degrading the ecological quality of the Aghien Lagoon system. These findings highlight the need for sustainable watershed management, improved sanitation practices, and regular monitoring to preserve this strategic freshwater resource for the Abidjan District.

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